

JUDICIAL WELLNESS INITIATIVE: A Conceptual Framework for Supporting the Sustainable System of Modern Judiciary

Solihin Niar Ramadhan

Andoolo District Court

solibiniar@gmail.com

Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has given us a valuable lesson that the most important asset of the judiciary besides its infrastructure, is the soundness of judges. Several factors such as ongoing family problems, high demand for judicial and non-judicial tasks, strict surveillance activities, and high public expectations of the court's performance increasingly affect judges' health extent. The amount of physical and psychological pressure experienced by judges in carrying out their duties directly impacts the court's performance and the quality of delivered judicial services. To support the implementation of the modern judicial system, the judge's physical and psychological soundness must be considered carefully. Unfortunately, the wellness protection of judges in Indonesia is still hitherto not a distinctive concern. Through a Business Ecosystem approach, the Judicial Wellness Initiative is formulated as an alternative solution that can be implemented as a synergy between IKAHI and other related parties for supporting the fulfilment of the judges' well-being. The Judicial Wellness Initiative scheme is hopefully expected to assist judges who are experiencing physical and mental health matters. Addressing the judges' health problems directly affects the quality of the court's performance and therefore, a sustainable modern judicial system can be realized.

Pandemi Covid-19 memberikan kita pelajaran berharga bahwa aset terpenting lembaga peradilan selain infrastrukturnya adalah kesehatan para hakim. Beberapa faktor seperti masalah keluarga yang berkepanjangan, tingginya tuntutan tugas yudisial dan non yudisial, ketatnya kegiatan pengawasan, dan ekspektasi publik yang tinggi terhadap kinerja pengadilan semakin mempengaruhi tingkat kesehatan hakim. Besarnya tekanan fisik dan psikis yang dialami oleh

hakim dalam menjalankan tugasnya berdampak langsung terhadap kinerja pengadilan dan kualitas pelayanan peradilan yang diberikan. Guna mendukung terselenggaranya sistem peradilan modern, kesehatan fisik dan psikis hakim harus diperhatikan dengan seksama. Sayangnya, perlindungan kesehatan hakim di Indonesia sampai saat ini masih belum menjadi perhatian tersendiri. Melalui pendekatan Business Ecosystem, Judicial Wellness Initiative dirumuskan sebagai solusi alternatif yang dapat diimplementasikan sebagai sinergi antara IKAHI dengan pihak terkait lainnya untuk mendukung pemenuhan kesejahteraan hakim. Skema Judicial Wellness Initiative diharapkan dapat membantu para hakim yang mengalami masalah kesehatan fisik dan mental. Penanganan masalah kesehatan hakim secara langsung mempengaruhi kualitas kinerja pengadilan sehingga sistem peradilan modern yang berkelanjutan dapat terwujud.

Keywords: The soundness of judges, judicial wellness initiative, IKAHI, modern judiciary.

Introduction

Parsing the Judge's Physical and Psychological Soundness

The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia has completely formulated modernization strategies for case management by empowering integrated legal services as the critical focus of judicial institutions.¹ The implementation of an online court system is a concrete example of the services and nowadays, it becomes the foreshadow of profound changes in the modern judicial business process. In the conception of the modern judiciary, the working pace of handling cases is an indicator of a judge's performance besides adherence, comprehensiveness, and conformity of case data on the court's system.

Judges are juridically state officials who have duties and responsibilities in examining and deciding cases. Entering the era of the modern judicial system, judges are required to have various kinds of expertise to deliver excellent judicial services. As human beings, there is a high possibility for judges to experience various challenges and obstacles in carrying out their duties, including physical and

¹ The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, *The Blueprint for Judicial Renewal 2010-2035*, available at <<https://www.mahkamahagung.go.id/>>, accessed on January 22nd, 2022. p.35.

psychological health problems. Eventually, this circumstance directly affects the performance of the judge in completing their assignment of trials and non-judicial tasks.

The sustainable modernization strategy of the judiciary must always be supported by taking into account the wellness status of judges as the main element of the judiciary. It is undoubtedly true that working under long-term pressure causes a high potential for harm to both judge's mental and physical health. That high level of psychological demands, such as rapid work and high-stress situations, leads to the risk of health problems. A recent Scandinavian scientist finding shows that stressors in working place are also risk factors for the common development of mental and physical disorders.² It affects judges' performance and task satisfaction when they are elevated intensity or longstanding.³

A survey held by Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) found that about 41% of workers feel exhausted because of several external factors like working remotely, working longer hours, high family expectations, security threats, and fear of unsafe working environments. In the end, it contributes to anxiety, depression, and loneliness conditions that can increase addictive substance consumption, stress, and depression.⁴ Therefore, a great number of multinational companies and foreign institutions pay attention to their employees' welfare as they realize that it has a great impact on the institution's performance.

The mental and physical aspect of judges is critically important to court performance as a whole. Unfortunately, the special attention that encourages awareness of the importance of mental and physical health in court environments is still not optimal. According to Steven Leifman, Associate Administrative Judge at the Eleventh Judicial Circuit Court of Florida, the only solution is empathy and concern

² Stephen Stansfeld and Bridget Candy, *Psychosocial work environment and mental health—a meta-analytic review*. Scand J Work Environ Health, 2006, p.444.

³ Jacqueline C. Vischer, *The Effects of the Physical Environment on Job Performance: Towards a Theoretical Model of Workspace Stress*, Wiley InterScience: Stress and Health, 2007, p.178.

⁴ The National Center for State Courts, *Addressing the Mental Health and Well-Being of Judges and Court Employees*, The National Judicial task Force to Examine State Courts' Response to Mental Illness, <https://www.ncsc.org/>, accessed on, accessed 22 January 2022, p.1;

among judges and court officials regarding physical and psychological health problems in their environment. This solution cannot be realized without the leadership role of the court chief and the active participation of all court officials together.⁵

As a comparison, in the United States of America, the National Center for State Courts (NCSC) has mapped out the initiatives of several state courts that work with various parties in developing programs related to mental health services for judges and court officials. For instance, in Florida, The Florida Judicial Wellness Program (FJWP) was established with the primary objective of helping judges with mental health problems, emotional disorders, and substance abuse. In Virginia, Virginia's Wellness Initiative was created to assist judges and court staff who have health problems with a particular focus on improving mental health and substance abuse.

In Indonesia, the initiative to stand up for judges' health insurance is still not optimal. For an instance, judges largely complain about the health services they received from Health Social Security Administering Agency (BPJS Kesehatan). A survey conducted by the Judicial Commission (KY) for the period 2016-2018 shows that in general, judges assess their health insurance and facilities to be inadequate (53.76%).⁶ Hitherto, the realization of proper wellness protection for Indonesian judges is still below expectations.

The Indonesian Judges Association (IKAHI) as the only professional association of judges has a significant contribution to contending the fulfilment of judges' constitutional rights for wellness protection. IKAHI's establishment objective is to improve the ideal and functional position of judges, in line with their pure and noble duties as state officials.⁷ Through this scientific work, the author will parse the concept of the Judicial Wellness Initiative by using the Business Ecosystem approach. In this article, the author examines two crucial issues:

⁵ Solihin Niar Ramadhan, *Mengurai Masalah Kesehatan Jiwa di Pengadilan (Sebuah Upaya Mewujudkan Pelayanan Prima)*, Dandapala Magazine Volume VII, 42nd Edition, July - August 2021, p.72-73.

⁶ The Judicial Commission of the Republic of Indonesia, *the Strategic Plan of the Judicial Commission 2020-2024*, <https://www.komisiyudisial.go.id>>, accessed 24 January 2022, p.19-20;

⁷ Article 4 : (1c) The IKAHI's Articles of Associations

1. The correlation between the sustainable modern judiciary and the judge's physical and psychological soundness.
2. The business ecosystem of the Judicial Wellness Program and its framework.

The Judicial Wellness Program: An Alternative Solution?

A. The Concept of Sustainable Modern Judiciary and Its Correlation to Judges' Physical and Psychological Soundness

“*Change and Reform*” become a special tagline to commemorate the great revolutionary movement of the conventional courts and tribunals towards a modern judicial system. The modernization of judicial infrastructures and the improvement of delivered public service quality is a substantial priority for courts around the globe nowadays. The Head of International Relations for the Judiciary of England and Wales, Lady Justice Arden even said that the judicial institutions should be continuing to change and develop themselves to fulfil the necessities of society.⁸

Gabrielle Appleby and Suzanne Le Mire argue the point of difference between the conventional judicial system and the modern one based on the values of the judiciary. Judicial independence and impartiality rightly remain the centrum principal of the judicial system whilst legitimacy, transparency, accountability, representativeness, and efficiency become the contemporary values emphasized by the modern judiciary.⁹ This means the more complex a system, the wider the values will exist.

The number of law experts trying to define the concept of the modern judicial system. The United Kingdom’s Ministry of Justice, for instance, undirectly defines the modern judiciary as an efficient court system with modern facilities – better information and technology infrastructure – that will assist judges to manage cases more efficiently. Moreover, they highlight that in the concept of the modern judiciary,

⁸ The Judicial Office, *The Judicial System of England and Wales: A Visitor’s Guide*, prepared by the Judicial Office International Team, <https://www.judiciary.uk/>, accessed 24 January 2022, P.28;

⁹ Gabrielle Appleby and Suzanne Le Mire, *Ethical Infrastructure for a Modern Judiciary*, Federal Law Review Vol.47 (3), Australian National University Press, 2019, P.335.

the judges can utterly focus on the cases that matter instead of taking the time to deal with administrative issues.¹⁰ Eventually, judges can deliver excellent public services that reduce unnecessary stress for victims and witnesses, and emotional turmoil experienced as an effect of major life events such as criminal activity, death, or divorce of the disputed parties.

The Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Macedonia also has its perspective and strategy structure about the modern judiciary. The Ministry believes that the concept of the modern judiciary was coined to increase the efficiency of the case management process.¹¹ The installation of the newest information technology infrastructure supported by the sustainable training of judges will simplify their court bureaucracy and manage cases more efficiently. They also assume the investment in technological aspects of the judicial system will eliminate the causes of justice delays, such as the complexity of trials procedure, the inappropriate organizational structure, and most important one is the non-transparent of the court's public information.

One concrete example of collaboration between information technology and case management is the e-Court, an early concept of the modern judiciary. In Malaysia, e-Court is the Malaysian Electronic Government project under the command of the Prime Minister's Legal Affairs Division. The Federal Court Chief Registrar's office is the implementing agency.¹² The complexity of e-Court in Malaysia depicts in the following flowchart.

¹⁰ The United Kingdom's Ministry of Justice, *Modernising Judicial Terms and Conditions: Government Response*, <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/>, accessed 24 January 2022, P.4.

¹¹ The Republic of Macedonia's Ministry of Justice, *Strategy on the Reform of the Judicial System with Annexes*, <https://www.legislationline.org/>, accessed 25 January 2022, P.6.

¹² Wan Satirah Wan Mohd Saman & Abrar Haider, *E-Court: Technology diffusion in court management*. 19th Americas Conference on Information Systems, AMCIS, 2013 - Hyperconnected World: Anything, Anywhere, Anytime. 2. P.6.

Source: Wan Satirah Wan Mohd Saman & Abrar Haider, 2013.

Figure 1. The Complexity of the e-Court System in the Federal Court of Malaysia, 2013.

In Indonesia, the concept of the modern judiciary was first formulated by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia (“the Supreme Court”) through the Blueprint of Judicial Renewal 2010-2035 (“the Blueprint”). According to the Blueprint, the concept of the modern judiciary is targeted at organizational design as a performance-based organization¹³ and knowledge-based organization¹⁴. Similar to the previous explanation of the modern judiciary concept, the

¹³ The performance-based organization is an initiative to encourage the Supreme Court and its judicial bodies to become more effective and efficient. It is visually marked by a clear separation between technical and non-technical matters, a clear distribution of tasks, responsibilities, and authority, the implementation of organizational performance and individual performance as a top priority, and all judicial apparatus have the skill to perform their performance appraisal.

¹⁴ The knowledge-based organization is an initiative to encourage the judicial apparatus to innovate more effective and efficient working methods. The research and development center has a strategic role to ensure the implementation of the development of legal substance and judicial policy updates of the Supreme Court.

Supreme Court confidently believes its main purpose is to effectively and efficiently implement the case management process. The following scheme illustrates the grand policy of case management modernization in the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia.

Source: *The Supreme Court's Blueprint of Judicial Renewal 2010-2035*, page 35.

Figure 2. The Grand Scheme of Judicial Reform by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, 2010.

Over a decade, the Supreme Court and its lower judicial institutions have implemented numerous policies to accelerate the transformation of the conventional judicial system to the modern judiciary. They make investments in judicial information technology infrastructure for handling cases and court administration tasks. The first initiative of the case management system enhancement in the judiciary was the implementation of the Case Tracking System (“CTS”), supported by USAID in 130 district courts by December 2012. This policy becomes the fundamental embryo of the modern courts implemented today.

In 2018, the Supreme Court and judicial bodies targeted to modernize its business process and public services by implementing the e-Court System, an electronic-based case management process to deliver judicial service more efficiently and effectively under the

provision of Supreme Court Regulation Number 3/2018 (“Perma 3/2018”). In the following year, the Supreme Court implemented the concept of electronic trials for private cases under the Supreme Court Regulation Number 1/2019 (“Perma 1/2019), replacing the previous ordinance. In September 2020, the Supreme Court began its innovation by issuing the Supreme Court Regulation Number 4/2020 (“Perma 4/2020) to implement the criminal case trials electronically as an effort to break the uncontrolled spread chain of Covid-19 in court. The following scheme can make it easier for you to understand the pattern of the e-court system in private case trials in the Indonesian Legal System.

Figure 3. The e-Court System in Private Case Trials in the Indonesian Legal System, 2022.

According to the flowchart above, the registered users or other users (“the plaintiff”) firstly access the e-court website on <https://ecourt.mahkamahagung.go.id/> to submit the lawsuit. On e-Filing services, they should choose the court for case registration and after receiving the registration number, the plaintiff should upload their required documents and fill out the parties’ identities. In the following step, they will be directed to the e-Payment service.¹⁵ After the billing is verified, their lawsuit and its additional documents will be processed by the court’s administrator through a local server (SIPP). The chief justice then appoints the panel of judges while the Clerk assigns to the substitution clerk and the bailiff. The panel of judges commands the bailiff to officially call the plaintiff and the defendant by using the e-Summons service¹⁶. After receiving the notification e-mail, the parties should come to the court for the first trial and mediation. If the mediation is successful, then the case examination will be dismissed by the panel of judges. On the contrary, if the mediation fails, the defendant will be asked for his approval to take the case through e-Litigation services.¹⁷ The final product of this system is an e-Verdict signed by the Clerk using e-Signature. At the end of the process, the parties can access and download the verdict electronically through the website.

The implementation of e-Court indicates that the Supreme Court has a forceful commitment to realize the concept of modern judiciary sustainably although many challenges.¹⁸ One of the challenges experienced by the Supreme Court and judicial institutions nowadays is judges’ physical and psychological soundness which occasionally goes unnoticed. It is undoubtedly true that the Covid-19 pandemic has

¹⁵ By registering cases online via e-Court, Registrants will automatically get an Estimated Downpayment Fee electronically (e-SKUM) and Payment Number (Virtual Account) which can be paid through available electronic devices (multi-channel). After the registrant makes a payment, the court gives the case number.

¹⁶ The summons and notification of the verdict are delivered to the parties via their email address and information on the summons can be viewed on the e-Court application.

¹⁷ The application supports the trial electronically (online) so that it can be sent electronic court documents such as the defendant’s response, *Replik*, *duplik*, and their conclusions.

¹⁸ The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, *The Annual Report of 2020: Optimization of the Sustainable Modern Judiciary on Covid-19 Pandemics*, <https://www.mahkamahagung.go.id/>, accessed 26 January 2022, P.12.

taught us that the most important asset of the judiciary besides its infrastructure, is the robustness of its employee. Ridwan Mansyur, the Clerk of the Supreme Court and the General Secretary of the Indonesian Judges Association even said that the modern courts are not only establishing the information technology infrastructure but also ensuring the employees' adaptation ability to the challenging conditions.¹⁹

In Indonesia, the modernization of the judicial system has directly challenged the judges' abilities to adapt the technological developments. In addition, the speedy and heavy workloads such as the development of Integrity Zone, the Quality Assurance Accreditation, the high-standard demand of public services for the disabilities, the internet interference on electronic trials, and working remotely away from family are the extraordinary problem that directly affects the judges' physical and mental health.

As a performance-based and knowledge-based judicial organization, the Supreme Court must pay attention to the soundness aspects of its employees, especially the judges as the main actor of judicial power. Unfortunately, the initiative to support judges' health insurance in Indonesia is still mazed hitherto. Even though according to Judge Steven Leifman, the Associate Administrative Judge for the Eleventh Judicial Circuit Court of Florida, the effective solution is empathy and attention between fellow judges and court officials towards mental and physical soundness issues in their environment.²⁰

As an exemplary comparison, we can imitate the efforts conducted by Judge Robert Henry, the chief judge of the United States Court of Appeals for the Tenth Circuit who directed the creation of the Judicial Health and Assistance Committee (JHAC) in 2009 to investigate and address judicial health issues. By using formal

¹⁹ Presented at the Technical Guidance and Judicial Administration Virtually by the Leaders of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia for 4 judicial institutions, Batam, 28 January 2022.

²⁰ The National Center for State Courts, *Addressing the Mental Health and Well-Being of Judges and Court Employees: A Pandemic Resource*, <https://www.ncsc.org/>, accessed 29 January 2022, P.3.

and informal research methods, the Committee successfully formulated several findings:²¹

1. Unrecognized and untreated health issues affect judges' mental or physical disability in longstanding and lead to unprofessional conduct complaints of judges. Eventually, it can eliminate public trust in judicial services.
2. Court performance and judicial officers' health status are reciprocally interrelated. The healthier the court officials, the higher the court's performance. It means, the physical and psychological soundness of judges is the fundamental factor affecting the courts' performance as a whole.
3. The natural characteristic of being a judge is apprehensive over criticism or embarrassment. That is the reason judges with health difficulties often are unwilling to recognize or request the medical aid needed. Chief judges, colleagues, court staff, and their family members are also disoriented to communicate appropriately with judges about their health or performance issues.
4. Judges are capable of assisting other working peers reciprocally to address their health issues before it causes performance degradation. If they are educated about mental and physical health challenges and risks, then they can obtain assistance voluntarily and escalate court performance.
5. The role of medical expertise is undoubtedly needed to address the health barrier experienced by judges. Determining the appropriate treatment of judges who have a high temper, physical pain, or overuse of alcohol, and other addictive substances completely becomes a psychiatrist's and medical doctor's competency.

According to those findings, it is proven that judicial responsibility comes with pressure and judges' soundness becomes a critical factor affecting the courts' performance.²² We should be concerned about judicial health status as these issues are a shared

²¹ Marcia S. Krieger, *et.al*, *JHEALTH: How The Tenth Circuits is Improving the Health and Performance of Federal Judges*, *Judicature: Volume 102 Number 1, Spring 2018*, P.51-52.

²² Gerald Lebovits, *Judicial Wellness: The Ups and Downs of Sitting New York Judges*, *New York State Bar Association Journal, Volume 89, Number 5, June 2017*, P.11.

responsibility. Maria Neira, Director of the Department of Public Health and Environment, World Health Organization, even said "*the wealth of business depends on the health of workers*".²³ To support the realization of the Supreme Court's vision as a sustainable modern judiciary, the human resources aspect must be physically, intellectually, and mentally healthy.

B. The Business Ecosystem of the Judicial Wellness Initiative

The author's perspective on this session will mainly be focused on the implementation of the government's healthcare program towards judges in Indonesia. The previous section of this paper has utterly explained the correlation between judges' soundness and court performance. The initiative to stand up for judges' health insurance in Indonesia is still not optimal though it has already been regulated under the law.

The judges' well-being has been regulated in the Government Regulation Number 94 of 2012 concerning the Financial Rights and Facilities of Judges ("PP 94/2012"). Underneath the provision of Article 2. e and Article 10 PP 94/2012, Indonesian judges are given health insurance by the provisions of the legislation. It means the health insurance provided by the Government should be based on Act Number 40 of 2004 regarding the National Social Security System ("UU 40/2004"). According to Article 19:(1) UU 40/2004, health insurance is administered nationally by state-owned and private health facilities in cooperation with the Social Security Administering Agency ("BPJS"). It means the judge's health insurance is juridically covered by BPJS.

The Judicial Commission of the Republic of Indonesia conducted a survey related to judges' health facilities in 2016-2018. The findings show that in general, 53.76% of judges assess their health insurance and facilities are inadequate, 24.73% of them felt it was quite adequate, 15.05% was adequate, 5.91% had never used it, and 0.54% abstained.²⁴ The survey results had already been submitted to the Supreme Court and BPJS as recommendations for decision-making improvement of

²³ The World Health Organization, *Healthy Workplaces: A Model for Action: For Employers, Workers, Policy-Makers, and Practitioners*, 2010, <https://www.who.int/>, accessed 31 January 2022, P.3

²⁴ The Regulation of the Judicial Commission of the Republic of Indonesia No.1 of 2020 regarding the Judicial Commission's Strategic Plan for 2020-2024, P.6.

health facilities for judges. However, the information about the improvement process is still opaque and debatable today.

The obscurity of information about the judge's healthcare program should be a valuable opportunity for all IKAHI personnel to synergy formulating alternative solutions. Somehow, empathy and attention between fellow judges towards soundness issues in their environment are fundamentally important and needed. Thus, the solution is the establishment of the Judicial Wellness Initiative ("the initiative"), an internal healthcare program to assist judges at all levels in addressing their soundness issues related to the working environment and personal life. The initiative provides benefits such as health and life insurance or a retirement plan, allowing them to focus on their work rather than having to worry about their health.²⁵

This program should be initiated by IKAHI as the association has the authority to assemble and coordinate judges around Indonesia. IKAHI can benchmark several progressions taken by the National Center for State Courts ("NCSC") in the United States of America. They had gathered specific wellness initiatives due to the state's court response in addressing the mental health and well-being issues in the judiciary.

Several courts across the U.S. have already developed innovative employee wellness programs that provide pandemic-related materials and promotional activities. In the State of Colorado, the Colorado Task Force on Judicial Soundness has assembled a website with resources for judges and other court employees to address various areas of wellness. In the state of Georgia, the Strategic Plan of Georgia's Judicial Council is established in partnership with the State Bar, including a wellness program that supports court officials. In the state of Utah, The Utah State Bar's Well-Being Committee for the Legal Profession is founded in cooperation with the Utah Supreme Court to focus on providing training, materials, and assistance for improving soundness in all legal professions. In the state of Virginia, Virginia's Wellness Initiative delivers support for judges and court officers with professional expertise in improving mental robustness and addressing addictive substance misappropriation.

²⁵ The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, *Resource Guide on Strengthening Judicial Integrity and Capacity*, <https://www.unodc.org/>, New York, 2011, P.27.

According to the examples above, the author believes that implementing the Initiative requires a synergy between IKAHI, its member, and several institutions providing healthcare and financial matters. It is nearly impossible to establish and run the Initiative without collaboration with third parties. Therefore, the business ecosystem analysis is needed to elaborate the workflow of the Initiative as a whole.

The term “Business Ecosystem” was originally described by James F. Moore, a US-American economic professor in the Harvard Business Review in 1993. He believed successful companies operate in a natural ecosystem and act simultaneously with other organizations for mutual benefits.²⁶ According to Moore, companies develop shared capabilities by working cooperatively and competitively in a business ecosystem to support new ideas and fulfil customer necessities.²⁷ The following business ecosystem flowchart illustrates how the conceptual framework of the Judicial Wellness Initiative operates.

²⁶ James F. Moore, *Predators and Prey: A New Ecology of Competition*, Harvard Business Review, May-June 1993, P.76.

²⁷ Simon Wieninger, *et.al*, *The Strategic Analysis of Business Ecosystems: New Conception and Practical Application of a Research Approach*, International Conference on Engineering Technology and Innovation, 2019, P.2.

Figure 4. The Business Ecosystem of the Judicial Wellness Initiative²⁸

On the scheme above we can see that the Judicial Wellness Initiative is a collaborative ecosystem, consisting of IKAHI, its member, the Central Administrator, Jasindo, and health service units. According to the flowchart, IKAHI as a professional association should collaborate with Jasindo, a state-owned enterprise on health insurance services. At first, judges are obligated to pay monthly contributions to IKAHI and the funds later became sustainable funding managed by the Association. In return, the Association provides a Member Card, connected directly to their bank account and insurance policy of Jasindo. The collected funds then become a monthly premium to Jasindo in financing the judge's health insurance. In a state of emergency, judges who experience health problems visit hospitals or clinics partner by showing their IKAHI member cards. The health service unit then provides the required health services and reports the medical actions taken and the costs incurred to Jasindo. Jasindo provides claim support to the hospitals and clinics for the conducted medical treatment. In the end, judges will focus on working to improve court performance and provide excellent public service for the community.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Conclusion

1. The sustainable development of a modern judiciary must be supported by adequate infrastructure. It is undoubtedly true that the concept of the Modern judiciary becomes an innovation for delivering judicial service more efficiently and effectively. On a contrary, the rapid-paced work, high demand for judicial and non-judicial tasks, strict surveillance activities, and high public expectations of the court performance become several stressors that negatively affect judges' well-being. The physical, psychological, and social soundness of judges must be a critical concern nowadays as it respectively interrelates to the court performance.

²⁸ The author chose PT. Asuransi Jasa Indonesia (Jasindo) as an example of the scheme refers to the statement of the Former Chief Justice of the Supreme Court on the Annual Reflection in Jakarta, December 27th, 2019.

2. Judges' health insurance in Indonesia is still not optimal though it has already been regulated under the Government Regulation Number 94 of 2012 concerning the Financial Rights and Facilities of Judges. The deficiency of the Government's concern for full fulfilment of judges' health insurance should not be a reason to complain. The Judicial Wellness Initiative is an alternative solution to fulfil the appropriate healthcare of judges. The business ecosystem analysis shows that it is nearly impossible to establish and operate the Judicial Wellness Initiative without collaboration with third parties.

Recommendation

The modernization policy of the judicial business process challenges judges' adaptation abilities to the new working environment. Our research suggests that the commitment and synergy between IKAHI, its member, and the related third parties to establish and realize the Judicial Wellness Initiative is currently needed. Indeed, special attention should be given to the activation of the Judicial Wellness Initiative to promote and support the sustainable modernization of the Judiciary. We should believe that judges can handle a great deal of stress if they have enhanced well-being. As said by Hon. Gerald Lebovits, the Supreme Court Justice in the New York States that "*justice suffers when a judge suffers physically or mentally*".

Bibliography

- Appleby, Gabrielle and Suzanne Le Mire, *Ethical Infrastructure for a Modern Judiciary*, Federal Law Review Vol.47 (3), Australian National University Press, 2019.
- Krieger, Marcia S., *et.al*, *JHEALTH: How The Tenth Circuits is Improving the Health and Performance of Federal Judges*, Judicature: Volume 102 Number 1, Spring 2018.
- Lebovits, Gerald, *Judicial Wellness: The Ups and Downs of Sitting New York Judges*, New York State Bar Association Journal, Volume 89, Number 5, June 2017.
- Moore, James F., *Predators and Prey: A New Ecology of Competition*, Harvard Business Review, May-June 1993.

Solihin Niar Ramadhan

JUDICIAL WELLNESS INITIATIVE: A Conceptual Framework for Supporting the Sustainable System of Modern Judiciary

Ramadhan, Solihin Niar, *Mengurai Masalah Kesehatan Jiva di Pengadilan (Sebuah Upaya Mewujudkan Pelayanan Prima)*, Dandapala Magazine Volume VII, 42nd Edition, July - August 2021.

Saman, Wan Satirah Wan Mohd and Abrar Haider, *E-Court: Technology diffusion in court management*. 19th Americas Conference on Information Systems, AMCIS - Hyperconnected World: Anything, Anywhere, Anytime, 2013.

Stansfeld, Stephen and Bridget Candy, *Psychosocial work environment and mental health—a meta-analytic review*. Scand J Work Environ Health, 2006.

The Government regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 94 of 2012 concerning Financial Rights and Facilities of Judges Under the Supreme Court.

The Judicial Commission of the Republic of Indonesia, *the Strategic Plan of the Judicial Commission 2020-2024*, <https://www.komisiyudisial.go.id>, accessed 24 January 2022.

The Judicial Office, *The Judicial System of England and Wales: A Visitor's Guide*, prepared by the Judicial Office International Team, <https://www.judiciary.uk/>, accessed 24 January 2022.

The National Center for State Courts, *Addressing the Mental Health and Well-Being of Judges and Court Employees*, The National Judicial task Force to Examine State Courts' Response to Mental Illness, <https://www.ncsc.org/>, accessed 22 January 2022.

The Regulation of the Judicial Commission of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2020 regarding the Judicial Commission's Strategic Plan for 2020-2024.

The Regulation of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2018 concerning the Administration of Cases in Electronic Courts.

The Regulation of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 1 of 2019 concerning Case Administration and Trials in Electronic Courts.

The Regulation of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 4 of 2020 concerning Criminal Cases Administration and Trial in Electronic Courts.

The Republic of Macedonia's Ministry of Justice, *Strategy on the Reform of the Judicial System with Annexes*, <https://www.legislationline.org/>, accessed 25 January 2022.

- The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, *The Annual Report of 2020: Optimization of the Sustainable Modern Judiciary on Covid-19 Pandemics*, <https://www.mahkamahagung.go.id/>, accessed 26 January 2022.
- The Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, *The Blueprint for Judicial Renewal 2010-2035*, <https://www.mahkamahagung.go.id/>, accessed 22 January 2022.
- The United Kingdom's Ministry of Justice, *Modernising Judicial Terms and Conditions: Government Response*, <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/>, accessed on 24 January 2022.
- The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, *Resource Guide on Strengthening Judicial Integrity and Capacity*, <https://www.unodc.org/>, New York, 2011, accessed 31 January 2022.
- The World Health Organization, *Healthy Workplaces: A Model for Action: For Employers, Workers, Policy-Makers, and Practitioners*, 2010, <https://www.who.int/>, accessed 31 January 2022.
- Vischer, Jacqueline C., *The Effects of the Physical Environment on Job Performance: Towards a Theoretical Model of Workspace Stress*, Wiley InterScience: Stress and Health, 2007.